

ESM G

Heterogeneity Estimates of the Pooled Correlations

Variable	H	E	X	A	C	O	D
H	-	.508 <i>(.747)</i>	.601 <i>(.807)</i>	.294 <i>(.780)</i>	.543 <i>(.821)</i>	.491 <i>(.705)</i>	.651 <i>(.804)</i>
E	.003 <i>(.008)</i>	-	.918 <i>(.947)</i>	.679 <i>(.829)</i>	.424 <i>(.712)</i>	.642 <i>(.836)</i>	.650 <i>(.801)</i>
X	.004 <i>(.012)</i>	.031 <i>(.048)</i>	-	.839 <i>(.906)</i>	.675 <i>(.838)</i>	.693 <i>(.848)</i>	.795 <i>(.854)</i>
A	.001 <i>(.007)</i>	.006 <i>(.014)</i>	.015 <i>(.027)</i>	-	.570 <i>(.771)</i>	.417 <i>(.628)</i>	.394 <i>(.668)</i>
C	.003 <i>(.011)</i>	.002 <i>(.007)</i>	.005 <i>(.012)</i>	.004 <i>(.009)</i>	-	.664 <i>(.876)</i>	.795 <i>(.864)</i>
O	.003 <i>(.007)</i>	.005 <i>(.014)</i>	.006 <i>(.015)</i>	.002 <i>(.005)</i>	.005 <i>(.017)</i>	-	.777 <i>(.862)</i>
D	.005 <i>(.010)</i>	.005 <i>(.011)</i>	.009 <i>(.013)</i>	.002 <i>(.005)</i>	.09 <i>(.013)</i>	.010 <i>(.018)</i>	-

Note. The lower off diagonal depicts the τ^2 estimates (random effects) of the pooled correlation coefficients from Table 2. The upper off diagonal is the relative heterogeneity estimate I^2 .

Estimates for the corrected correlations are given in parentheses() and *italics*.